

OPEN HOLE FATIGUE OF STITCHED AND UNSTITCHED CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Tension-compression open hole fatigue tests were conducted to determine the effect of stitching on the delamination damage progression and fatigue life of notched carbon/epoxy laminates. The specimens were made from uniweave fabric stitched with Kevlar or Dyneema thread at various stitch densities and subsequently impregnated by resin transfer moulding. The specimens had a 6 mm hole drilled at their centre and were supported by anti-buckling plates with a 25 x 62 mm window surrounding the hole. They were cycled, up to a maximum of 100,000 cycles, between the tension and compression loads required to achieve, far-field strains of $\pm 0.35\%$. It was concluded that the low density Kevlar stitched specimens had better fatigue resistance than the unstitched specimens and the low density stitched Dyneema specimens had even better fatigue resistance. On the other hand, the fatigue resistance of the high density stitched Kevlar specimens was inferior to that of the unstitched specimens.

KEYWORDS: open hole fatigue, stitched composites, carbon/epoxy composites, delamination progression

INTRODUCTION

The manufacture of composites from stitched woven carbon cloth and impregnated by a liquid moulding techniques, such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), has the potential to produce low cost high quality components with improved resistance to delamination. The increase in damage tolerance and resistance of such stitched composite depends on many parameters such as laminate thickness and stitching yarn properties and density. A major motivation for stitching preforms is the potential to greatly reduce the cost of component manufacture by reducing RTM tooling costs and to reduce the number of components in the structure, hence reducing the assembly costs. Consequently, stitched preforms may be used solely for manufacturing considerations, even for configurations which do not benefit from increased damage tolerance. To facilitate the use of such materials in aircraft production, it is essential that their mechanical properties are characterised.

To this end, a collaborative program between The Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced composite Structures (CRC-ACS), and National Aerospace Laboratory, The Netherlands (NLR) was undertaken to explore the mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminates stitched with Kevlar or Dyneema. Preliminary results of the static properties have been

reported by Thuis and Bron [1]. This follows previous studies at the CRC-ACS on the tension [2], compression [3] and compression-after-impact [3-5] of Kevlar stitched carbon/epoxy laminates. An extensive review of the effect of stitching on the in-plane mechanical properties of fibre reinforced plastics has been conducted by Mouritz et. al. [6] where they summarise the limited amount of work which has been reported to date on the fatigue properties of stitched composites.

Most reported fatigue studies of stitched composites involved compression-compression loading. Lubowinsky and Poe [7] found that stitching improved fatigue life, despite the local damage and fibre distortion caused by stitching. On the other hand, others (eg Furrow et al. [8]) found that stitching did not effect the fatigue performance. In particular Portanova and Poe [9] found open hole fatigue performance was unaffected by stitching. Shah Khan and Mouritz [10] have studied the fatigue performance of stitched and unstitched GFRP under zero-to-tension cycling and they report a substantial reduction in fatigue life due to stitching. This was attributed, in part to damage caused by stitching. Xiao and Bathias [11] have conducted tension fatigue tests on unstitched notched (open hole) and unnotched woven glass/epoxy laminates and they have reported that the notched and un-notched laminates had the same ratios of fatigue strength to ultimate tensile strength.

An investigation has been undertaken to determine the effect of stitching on the open-hole fatigue performance of carbon/epoxy laminates subject to tension-compression cyclic loading. In particular the effect of stitching on the progression of delamination has been studied. This paper presents preliminary results of this investigation.

SPECIMENS MANUFACTURE AND DEFINITION

The test specimens used for the present study were machined from panels produced by impregnating stitched and unstitched woven carbon preforms with epoxy resin, using the Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process.

The preforms were manufactured from 17 layers of Ciba Composites GU-230-E01 uniweave fabric with a lay-up of [45, -45, 45, 0, -45, 90, 45, -45, 0, -45, 45, 90, -45, 0, 45, -45, 45]. The warp tows were 3K T300 (or equivalent) and they formed 90% of the fibres. The weft included special yarns to facilitate resin infusion by RTM. The fabric had a fine surface spray of partially cured epoxy which facilitated preforming.

Some of the preforms were stitched, respectively, with a twisted 40 tex (2×20) Kevlar thread or a twisted 16.5 tex (3 x 5.5) Dyneema thread. A modified lock-stitch was used, where the knot was adjusted to lie within the top fabric layer. The stitch rows were oriented at 0°, with a stitch pitch of 3.6 mm and spacing of 7.0 mm to produce a stitch density of four stitches per cm². A high density stitching of ten stitches per cm² was achieved by spacing the stitch rows at 3.5 mm and reducing the stitch pitch to 2.9 mm. Further details of the stitch geometry are presented by Leong et al. [5]

The preforms were impregnated, using the closed mould RTM process, with Ciba Composites LY 5052 epoxy resin, in conjunction with HY 5052. They were cured for four hours at 55°C. The nominal panel thickness was 3.5 mm, giving a fibre volume fraction (carbon only) of 60%. In fact, the specimens had an average thickness of 3.66 mm (standard deviation 1.6%) with a corresponding fibre volume fraction of 57%.

The specimens, of dimension 50 x 250 mm and described in Fig. 2, were cut from the panels so that the stitch rows were parallel to their loading direction. A 6.0 mm hole was drilled in their centre and left in the as-drilled condition. Steel end tabs and aluminium clip-gauge tabs, as shown in Figs. 1 and 2, were bonded to the specimens using Redux 420A/B adhesive and cured for 4 hours at 50°C. The aluminium clip-gauge tabs, of dimension 5 x 10 mm were located so that their centreline was 10 mm to one side of the centre of the hole and the gap between them was 14 mm to accommodate the clip-gauge extensometer (MTS model 632.03C-02).

Fig. 1: Schematic of fatigue test showing anti-buckling guides, clip gauge and clip gauge tabs

Fig. 2: Fatigue specimens and steel tab lay-out

TEST PROCEDURE

Four specimens were tested, of each of the four stitch configurations, which were: unstitched, low density Kevlar stitching, high density Kevlar stitching and low density Dyneema stitching. Specimen details and their uncycled static ultimate tensile (UTS) and compressive (UCS) are summarised in Table 1. Each of the specimen was allocated a four digit identification number. The first two digits define the specimen type and the following two digits allowed discrimination among individual specimens. For example, specimens 1217 and 1220 are two of the Kevlar low density stitched specimens.

Table 1: Specimen details and static strengths

Specimen Type	Stitching		No. Cycled	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	
	Type	Density /cm ²		Tension	Compression
11	unstitched		4	335	223
12	Kevlar 40 tex	4	4	323	226
13	Kevlar 40 tex	10	4	321	n/a
15	Dyneema 16.5 tex	4	4	326	243

Each specimen was loaded, at room temperature, in tension/compression fatigue at a frequency of 5 Hz under load control, between the tension and compression loads required to achieve, respectively, far-field strains of +/- 0.35% in the uncycled specimen. During the test these strains increased considerably. Those specimens which did not fail sooner, were subjected to 100,000 cycles, after which their residual compressive strength was measured. At the beginning of the test and at 10,000 cycle intervals the specimens were subject to visual inspection, an ultrasonic inspection and a strain survey. During cycling the specimen was constrained from buckling by antibuckling guides. Details of the test procedure and equipment are presented below.

Fatigue Cycling

The tests were conducted at room temperature (18°C to 24°C) using a 100 kN MTS servo-hydraulic test machine fitted with hydraulic grips and controlled by a MTS Teststar control and data acquisition system, which was also used for data acquisition.

The specimens were cycled, under load control, with constant amplitude at a frequency of 5Hz to a maximum of 100,000 cycles. The maximum and minimum loads were chosen to correspond, respectively to a far-field strain of +/- 0.35% in the uncycled specimen. They were typically 20 kN and 19 kN respectively. Such high strain levels were chosen so that significant fatigue damage would occur, in order to assess the effects of stitching. This level was in fact appropriate as evidenced by the fact that five of the sixteen specimens tested failed at fewer than 100,000 cycles. The tests were interrupted at 10,000 cycle intervals in order to conduct strain surveys and allow inspection of the specimen.

In order to determine the load limits, one specimen for each type had a strain gauge located 25 mm above the centre of the hole which measured the far-field strain. This specimen was loaded in tension, under load control, at a rate of 125 N/sec until a strain of 0.35% was reached, at which time the test was terminated. The corresponding load was used as the maximum load for subsequent cycling. The test was repeated in compression in order to determine the minimum load. The same fatigue profile was used for all specimens of one type.

Anti-Buckling Guides

The specimens, prior to testing, were fitted with an anti-buckling guide so as to leave an unsupported region of 60 mm x 25 mm around the hole. The configuration of these guides is shown in Fig. 1. To accommodate the compressive strain, there was a 1 mm gap between the top and bottom of the guides and the respective end-tabs. The specimen was clamped between the specimen with the aid of bolts which were adjusted until finger-tight. At each 1,000 cycle inspection interval the guides were removed and refitted before subsequent testing.

The out-of-plane deflection of a number of specimens was measured during a number of strain surveys with the aid of an LVDT located close to the hole. In the worst case an out-of-plane displacement of 0.04 mm was measured at a load of 22 kN, which corresponds to a maximum bending stress of less than 2% of the total compressive stress. This demonstrated that the guides were effective.

In-Situ Ultrasonic C-Scan

An in-situ ultrasonic scanner, based on the time of flight technique, was used to monitor damage growth without the necessity to remove the specimen from the test machine. The system uses a semi-impervious membrane and water couplant to transmit the signals from a 10 MHz focused ultrasonic transducer and it has a resolution of 1 mm². A description of the system, its operation, calibration and validation is reported by Galea and Saunders [12].

Fig. 3: C-Scan of stitched specimen 1320 after 30,000 cycles

At each inspection interval the antibuckling-guide was removed and the specimen was C-scanned. Fig. 3 is an example of such a C-Scan which clearly shows the damage area extending laterally from the hole. The clip-gauge tabs caused interference which resulted in the apparent damage pattern at the top and the bottom of the right hand side of the hole.

Strain Surveys

The strain surveys which were conducted at intervals of 10,000 cycles, involved loading the specimen progressively, at a rate of 500N/sec, up to the maximum load then decreasing the load, at the same rate, down to the minimum load (compression) and again increasing the load to zero. Data was recorded, at 0.25 second intervals, for applied load and strain from the clip gauge. The slope of the resulting load vs strain plot, called the load/strain parameter (LSP) was monitored. The change in the LSP is a manifestation of the extent of material degradation which caused a loss of stiffness in the region of the hole and a consequential redistribution of the load path. The load/strain ratio (LSR) was defined as the ratio of the LSP to its value for the uncycled specimen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For all specimens delamination cracks were visible in the sides of the hole after the first 10,000 cycles. These cracks progressed laterally from tool marks in the wall of the hole. In

most cases the initial rapid growth of the delamination reached a plateau and subsequently resumed its growth (eg Fig.4^a). The load/strain ratio followed a similar, but inverse, progression (eg Fig.4^b). A total of five of the 16 specimens tested failed at fewer than 100,000 cycles. As is to be expected from fatigue test there was considerable scatter in the data. However, there are indications that the low density Kevlar stitched specimens had better fatigue resistance than the unstitched specimens and the low density stitched Dyneema specimens had even better fatigue resistance. On the other hand, the fatigue resistance of the high density stitched Kevlar specimens was inferior to that of the unstitched specimens.

Fig. 4^a: Delamination progression unstitched specimens

Fig. 4^b: Progression of load/strain ratio unstitched specimens

Damage Progression

Various forms of damage were manifest as the cycling progressed these included: delamination, transverse cracks, matrix and fibre pulverisation and stitch debonding. There were indications that delamination and transverse crack growth were arrested for a while at the stitch rows, however, they were not conclusive.

Delamination damage growth was monitored via C-Scan and the progression of changes in the load strain ratio gave an indication of general damage accumulation and growth. Figs. 4^a to 7^a describe the behaviour of the delamination growth where, typically, the initial rapid growth reached a plateau and subsequently resumed its growth. Figs. 4^b to 7^b describe the progression of the LSR, which is a manifestation of the extent of material degradation. It, typically, followed a similar, but inverse, progression to the delamination growth.

Fig. 5^a: Delamination progression Kevlar low density stitched specimens

Fig. 5^b: Progression of load/strain ratio Kevlar low density stitched specimens

Fig. 6^a: Delamination progression Kevlar high density stitched specimens

Fig. 6^b: Progression of load/strain ratio Kevlar low high density stitched specimens

Fig. 7^a: Delamination progression Dyneema low density stitched specimens

Fig. 7^b: Progression of load/strain ratio Dyneema low density stitched specimens

Visual Inspection

Fig. 8 shows an example of a delamination crack in the rim of the hole initiating from a tool mark. Such cracks were seen in all specimens at the first inspection interval. The number and extent of such delamination cracks increased as the tests progressed. This delamination, on both sides of the hole, was also manifest in sublaminar buckling, which was observable during cycling and first appeared at about 20,000 cycles. The buckling region grew in an intermittent fashion for both stitched and unstitched specimens. There was a qualitative impression that the progression of this buckling was arrested by the stitch rows. However, an attempt to quantify this was inconclusive. Debonding of stitches at the surface was evidenced by slight relative motion of stitches to the surface of the specimen. This appeared as early as 20,000 cycles and appeared to be associated with and preceded the sublaminar buckling.

Fig. 8: Delamination crack in hole rim

Transverse cracks were observed on the surface of the specimens. These cracks originated at the three o'clock and nine o'clock positions at the rim of the hole and progressed at 45° along the direction of the surface warp tows. In most cases only one crack formed in each direction but occasionally there were two. Matrix crazing subsequently appeared close to the cracks. After 100,000 cycles these cracks were between 5 mm and 15 mm long for the various specimens. As was the case with the delaminations, these cracks grew in an intermittent fashion for both the stitched and unstitched specimens. Again, there was a qualitative impression that their progression was arrested by the stitch rows. However, an attempt to quantify this was inconclusive.

After about 50,000 cycles, debris comprising both black and white particles were evident and the surface of the specimen, in the vicinity of the damage, became rough. These are indications that pulverisation of both the matrix and fibres had occurred. A microscopic examination of the cycled specimens has yet to be conducted.

C-Scan

The progression of delamination width is presented in Figs. 4^a to 7^a. The value plotted is the sum of the widths of the delaminations on each side of the hole, measured between the edge of the hole to the lateral extent of the C-Scan plot. As mentioned earlier the resolution of the C-Scan plot was 1 mm and it is estimated that the accuracy of the measurements was ± 1 mm.

The window in the anti-buckling guide was 25 mm wide, consequently, sublaminar buckling would have been constrained for delamination widths greater than 19 mm. The maximum

width for specimens which survived 100,000 cycles was 17 mm for specimens 1217 and 1221. The specimens that failed did so within 10,000 cycles after the delamination width reached the window. This indicates that sublaminar buckling was not the sole failure mechanism.

The delamination width grew in an intermittent fashion for both the stitched and unstitched specimens. An attempt to correlate the position of the plateaux with the stitch line positions was inconclusive.

Load/Strain Ratio

The progression of the load/strain ratio (LSR) for each of the specimens is presented in Figs. 4^b to 7^b. The LSP is not only a measure of the stiffness of the material in the region of the clip gauge, but it also a measure of load redistribution due to damage and consequent changes in local stiffness in other regions of the material. In particular a local reduction in stiffness in the region of the hole which does not extend to the location of the clip gauge will nevertheless cause a reduction in the LSP and consequently the LSR. Delamination damage, particularly when sublaminar buckling occurs, will cause such a reduction in stiffness. However, other forms of damage, such as microcracking, will also cause a stiffness reduction. The fact that the LSR follows the same (inverse) progression as that of the delamination damage does not necessarily mean that delamination was the dominant damage mode, since the other forms of damage may have progressed at a similar rate. The second change in slope of the LSR curve may be due to the delamination, on the clip-gauge side, passing the clip-gauge position. A comparison of the number of cycles at which these two events occurred showed good correlation. This is not always evident from Figs. 4^a to 7^a, because they record the total of the delamination widths on each side, which were not always equal. A more extensive discussion of these issues will be presented elsewhere.

Table 2: Fatigue life or damage at 100,000 cycles

Specimen	Stitching		Load Range (kN)		Fatigue Life (cycles)	At 100,000 cycles	
	Type	Density	Tens.	Comp.		Delamination width (mm)	Load/Strain Ratio
1117	unstitched		21.8	20.3	100,000 ⁺ *	14	0.74
1120					100,000 ⁺	8	0.80
1121					96,260	-	-
1122					74,354	-	-
1217	Kevlar	Low	20.8	19.7	100,000 ⁺ *	17	0.65
1220					100,000 ⁺ *	9	0.72
1221					100,000 ⁺	17	0.78
1222					100,000 ⁺	9	0.78
1317	Kevlar	High	21.8	20.2	53,236	-	-
1320					92,500	-	-
1321					74,404	-	-
1322					100,000 ⁺	10	0.72
1517	Dyneema	Low	20.2	18.9	100,000 ⁺	9	0.92
1520					100,000 ⁺	16	0.73
1521					100,000 ⁺	13	0.81
1522					100,000 ⁺	6	0.88

*fatigue life < 110,000 cycles estimated on the basis of damage progression

Effects of Stitching

As may be seen from the data presented in Table 2, the fatigue performance of the high density Kevlar stitched specimens was inferior to that of the unstitched specimens. None of the low density Kevlar and Dyneema stitched specimens failed below 100,000 cycles indicating a superior fatigue performance to that of unstitched specimens. However, this may have been influenced by the slightly lower (about 5%, see Table 2) cycling load range. As described earlier, the load range was chosen, for each specimen type, to give a strain range of $\pm 0.35\%$ for the uncycled specimens. In order to facilitate the comparison of fatigue performance, it would perhaps have been preferable to use the same load range for all specimen types.

A comparison of the damage progression for the low density Kevlar and Dyneema stitched specimens (Figs. 5 and 7) shows that the Dyneema stitched specimens have superior fatigue performance. This is particularly evident from a comparison of the progression of their LSRs (Figs. 5^b and 7^b). This may be related to the higher compressive strength measured for the Dyneema stitched specimens compared to the unstitched and low density Kevlar stitched specimens (Table 1). Unfortunately the compressive test results for the high density stitched specimens is unavailable for comparison. The improved compressive and fatigue performance may be due to the smaller diameter (~20%) of the Dyneema thread which would lead to less fibre distortion due to stitching.

From visual observations there were indications that the stitch rows provided some resistance to the growth of transverse cracks and sublaminar buckling, however an attempt to quantify this effect was inconclusive. No correlation was found between the positions of stitches and the plateaux in the progression of delamination damage. This may be because the length scale of the damage is such as to preclude steady-state crack bridging.

From the above results, the indications are, that the through-thickness reinforcement effect of stitching does enhance fatigue performance to some extent. On the other hand, the fibre misalignment caused by stitching degrades compression and compressive fatigue performance. It would appear that there is an optimum combination of stitch density and fibre diameter which will maximise the fatigue performance.

CONCLUSIONS

Tension-compression open hole fatigue tests were conducted on carbon/ epoxy laminates made from uniweave fabric stitched with Kevlar or Dyneema thread at various stitch densities. Four specimens from each type were cycled up to a maximum of 100,000 cycles. Based on the limited number of specimens tested, the following conclusions may be made on the effect of stitching on their open hole fatigue performance.

- The fatigue performance of the high density Kevlar stitched specimens was inferior to that of the unstitched specimens.
- The fatigue performance of the low density Kevlar stitched specimens was inferior to that of the low density Dyneema stitched specimens. This is possibly because of the smaller diameter of the Dyneema thread.

- There are strong indications that the fatigue performance of both, the low density Kevlar and Dyneema stitched specimens, was superior to that of the unstitched specimens.
- For all specimens there was evidence of delamination after the first 10,000 cycles.
- There was no evidence that stitching arrested the progression of delamination damage.
- There were indications, based on visual examination, that the stitch rows temporarily arrested the propagation of transverse cracks and sublaminar buckling. However, attempts to quantify this were inconclusive.

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